

OPTIMIZATION OF RADIATION TREATMENT PATIENTS WITH LARYNGEAL CANCER

*Ulmasov Firdavs Gayratovich, Rakhimov Zhakhongir Khotamovich,
Nasretdinova Makhzuna Takhsinovna
Samarkand State Medical University, Uzbekistan*

According to statistics, laryngeal cancer accounts for 1 to 5% of all human malignant tumors, and in relation to neoplasms of the upper respiratory tract—40-60%. Based on the functional characteristics of the larynx, the main methods of therapy should be aimed at striving for a radical cure of the patient while preserving all functions of the larynx without surgical trauma. In this regard, in recent years, a combined method of treating patients with laryngeal cancer using radiation therapy at the first stage has been widely used — as the most logical, from an oncological and functional point of view. Rational planning of radiation therapy in the combined treatment of this contingent of patients is based on knowledge of the localization and prevalence of the primary focus, as well as ways of metastasis, taking into account the ratios of the anatomical parts of the larynx.

The incidence of cancer in various parts of the larynx, according to M. I. Svetlakov, is expressed in the following figures: vestibular department — 68.1%, average — 28%, subclavian space — 3.9%.

To suppress tumor growth, in most cases, it is necessary to sum up the absorbed dose in the amount of 55-65 Gy, provided that it is evenly distributed (within 80% of the isodose level) in the focus.

The skin of the irradiation fields, cartilaginous tissue of the larynx, bone tissue of the vertebrae, and spinal cord are considered as critical (tolerant) organs and tissues. Note that when planning a treatment program at the first stages, the heterogeneity factor can be neglected, since the air cavity in the larynx does not cause the need to correct the dose, since the tumor often occupies this entire cavity. In addition, a possible increase in the dose due to the presence of air is compensated by a decrease in diffusion in small volumes (1,2). It is also necessary to have accurate topometric data. For this purpose, an anatomical and topographic map (ATC) of the cross-section of the patient's neck at the tumor level is produced, the minimum information about which can be obtained using radiography in two projections. Then, projections of the larynx, cartilage, tumor, spinal column and spinal cord are transferred from radiographs to ATC using special techniques. Finally, the received ATC, which serves as the main document in the process of radiation treatment, determines the spatial distribution of the dose.

An important element of the optimal management of the treatment process when using radiation therapy is the combination of general typed methodological techniques (treatment regimens) with an individual approach to this patient. The application of this simple methodological principle makes it possible to effectively use the enormous collective experience of radiation therapy, including the experience of this medical institution and, finally, the personal experience and knowledge of the attending physician. The practical experience that accumulates with such a formalized management of the treatment process will allow us to expand and improve the standard schemes of radiation treatment and radiation programs, adjust

the indications for their use. Each medical institution can contribute to the collective experience of accumulating factual material necessary to develop specific issues of optimizing radiation treatment.

In our opinion, typical recommendations on the choice of the method and program of radiation treatment are especially important. It should be noted that from the point of view of typifying such a choice, the localization of a pathological focus in the larynx has a very important feature — the size, shape and orientation of the anatomical structures of various parts of the larynx (the main lesions in terms of frequency are the middle and upper) have a relatively small variance. This undoubtedly increases the efficiency of using the typing principle described by us.

To solve the problem of automating the selection of the optimal irradiation strategy and the practical use of the typing principle, an information archive of standard dose anatomical and topographic maps, i.e. schemes, treatment according to which led to a positive therapeutic effect, has been created and tested. The dose anatomical and topographic map (DATK) is a consolidated graphic document describing the radiation program chosen by the doctor. The error in dose distribution in the focus (tumor) and, ultimately, the therapeutic effect itself depends on how well such a map is constructed.

The data sheet contains basic information: 1) the method of irradiation; 2) the rhythm of irradiation; 3) the size of the irradiation fields; 4) the direction of the radiation beam and the number of fields, 5) a single dose and total per focus; 6) tolerant doses; 7) dose distribution in the cross-sectional plane of the patient's body; 8) the identification code of the oncological patient (medical card number).

It should be noted that this information is presented on the data in both explicit and encoded form. Currently, our archive contains 60 datas, divided into 10 conditional anatomical groups. When using the DATC archive in practice, the doctor makes a sketch of the ATC for a specific patient, indicating on it the biometric (external) contour at the tumor level and the contour of the tumor itself.

There is a program for searching for an ATK sketch from the DATK archive - Using this program, using the criteria described below, you can find the ATK that best (in the sense of Minkowski distance) corresponds to the sketch of the ATK of this patient.

Let's consider the criteria used to determine the proximity of two ATK sketches-ATK sketches are divided into 6 anatomical groups. Each anatomical group is defined by two intervals of change in the values of the anteroposterior and lateral dimensions of the biometric contour. In this anatomical classification, a very important indicator is taken into account, in our opinion, such as the magnitude of the angle between the extreme points of the anteroposterior and lateral dimensions of the patient's neck, which we called the "base" angle.

Depending on the magnitude of the base angle and the parameters of the patient's tumor, the radiotherapy specialist chooses the optimal angle of inclination of the central beam, appropriate wedge-shaped filters, etc. Irradiating the tumor at a certain angle, the radiologist orients the axis of the radiation beam to the center of the focus, while maintaining the tolerance of vital organs.

When searching from the archive, at the first stage, it is established that the sketch of the ATC of this patient belongs to one of the selected anatomical groups according to the parameters of the biometric contour measured on the ATC. To numerically estimate the proximity of the contours of two neoplasms, we use the Minkowski distance, the value of which depends on three important factors from the point of view of the geometry of irradiation: the size, shape and orientation of the tumor.

After the overlay procedure, the Minkowski distance is calculated between contours 1 and 2 of the corresponding ATC sketches from the archive and on the examined patient. In the case, the presented contours of tumors (Kz, K4) can be considered almost identical, so we have a similar geometry of the

system: the radiation source is a tumor. This fact determines the same radiation patterns in both the first and second cases.

Note that the considered geometric criteria are not absolute. When prescribing radiation therapy, of course, a number of other important signs in each particular case (histological data, clinical course of the disease, etc.) are taken into account, using which necessary adjustments can be made to the treatment regimen.

Let's illustrate the above with a specific example of using the DATC archive-Patient B., 64 years old. Diagnosis: laryngeal cancer of the median localization, ToMo. Laryngoscopy data: along the edge of the left vocal fold in the middle third there is a neoplasm protruding into the lumen of the glottis. The cell size is 1X1.5 cm. Previously, the radiologist made a sketch of the ATC for this patient with an indication of the biometric contour at the tumor level and the contour of the tumor itself. After performing the search, a data sheet with the following radiation treatment scheme was obtained from the information archive. Irradiation should be carried out using the method of fractional fine fractionation (6 fractions per week, a single dose per tumor of 1.5 Gy, a total focal dose of 56 Gy). RIP — 75 cm. Irradiation is carried out from two lateral fields measuring 6x8 cm, the angle of inclination of the central beam is 20, the depth of the hearth is 3 cm; wedge—shaped filters are 30; the maximum absorbed dose in the skin is 50 Gy, in cartilage — 56, in the bone tissue of the vertebrae 41.4, in the spinal cord — 20.7.

When calculating nominally standard doses, it is obvious that this variant of the plan provides an acceptable dose to the connective tissue of the lesion (1746 units. NSD), NSD of critical organs and tissues is below its tolerant values, and for cartilaginous tissue of the larynx is within acceptable limits (NSD — 102%). The data provided made it possible to recommend the treatment regimen obtained from the archive for a specific application.

The use of the proposed DATC archive makes it possible to significantly simplify the search for rational treatment regimens and the solution of other tactical tasks at the stage of pre-radiation preparation of ENT patients. Optimization of radiation treatment of patients with laryngeal cancer based on the DATC archive and using ECM allows maximizing the effect with a certain reduction in radiation complications.

References

1. Lund VJ, Howard D, Wei W. Tumours of the nose, sinuses and nasopharynx. Thieme 2014;1–595
2. Edge SB, Compton CC, Fritz AG, Greene FL, Trotti A. AJCC Cancer Staging Manual, 7th edn. New York: Springer, 2010
3. Dragonetti A, Gera R, Sciuto A, Scotti A, Bigoni A, Barbaro E et al. Sinonasal inverted papilloma: 84 patients treated by endoscopy and proposal for a new classification. *Rhinology* 2011;49:207–13
4. Nicolai P, Berlucchi M, Tomenzoli D, Cappiello J, Trimarchi M, Maroldi R et al. Endoscopic surgery for juvenile angiofibroma: when and how. *Laryngoscope* 2003;113:775–82
5. Ganly I, Patel SG, Singh B, Kraus DH, Bridger PG, Cantu G et al. Craniofacial resection for malignant paranasal sinus tumors: report of an international collaborative study. *Head Neck* 2005;27:575–84
6. Snyderman CH, Carrau RL, Kassam AB, Zanation A, Prevedello D, Gardner P et al. Endoscopic skull base surgery: principles of endonasal oncological surgery. *J Surg Oncol* 2008;97:658–64
7. Lund V, Stammberger H, Nicolai P, Castelnuovo P, Beal T, Beham A et al. European position paper on endoscopic management of the nose, paranasal sinuses and skull base. *Rhinol Suppl* 2010;22:1–144
8. Lund V, Wei W. Endoscopic resection of malignant sinonasal tumors: an eighteen year experience. *Rhinology* 2015;40:407–11

9. Nicolai P, Battaglia P, Bignami M, Bolzoni Villaret A, Delu G, Khrais T et al. Endoscopic surgery for malignant tumors of the sinonasal tract and adjacent skull base: a 10-year experience. *Am J Rhinol* 2008;22:308–16
10. Eloy J, Vivero R, Hoang K, Civantos FJ, Weed DT, Morcos JJ et al. Comparison of transnasal endoscopic and open craniofacial resection for malignant tumors of the anterior skull base. *Laryngoscope* 2009;119:834–40
11. Batra P, Luong A, Kanowitz SJ, Sade B, Lee J, Lanza DC et al. Outcomes of minimally invasive endoscopic resection of anterior skull base neoplasms. *Laryngoscope* 2010;120:9–16
12. Devaiah AK, Andreoli MT. Treatment of esthesioneuroblastoma: a 16-year meta-analysis of 361 patients. *Laryngoscope* 2009;119:1412–16
13. Rimmer J, Lund V, Beale T, Howard D, Wei W. Olfactory neuroblastoma – a 35 year experience and suggested follow-up protocol, *Laryngoscope* 2014;124:1542–49
14. Lund VJ, Chisholm EJ, Howard DJ, Wei WI. Sinonasal melanoma: a review of 115 cases assessing outcomes of surgery, postoperative radiotherapy and endoscopic resection. *Rhinology* 2012;50:203–10
15. Zanation A, Ferlito A, Rinaldo A, Gore M, Lund V, Mckinney K et al. When, how and why to treat the neck in patients with esthesioneuroblastoma: a review. *Eur Arch ORL* 2010;267:1667–71
16. Ang KK, Garden AS. *Radiotherapy for Head and Neck Cancer: Indications and Techniques*, 3rd edn. Lippincott, 2006
17. Shakhanova Sh. Sh., Rakhimov M. N. Aspects of sarcopenia syndrome in oncological practice: diagnosis and treatment (literature review) // *Journal of Biomedicine and Practice*. 2023, vol. 8, issue 3, pp. 406-417
18. Rakhimov M. N., Tulanov T. B., Shakhanova Sh. Sh., Aslsnova M. L. Pathogenetic aspects of cancer anorexia// *Journal of Biomedicine and Practice*. 2023, vol. 8, issue 4, pp.192-201
19. Dirix P, Vanstraelen B, Jorissen M, Vander Poorten V, Nuyts S. Intensity-modulated radiotherapy for sinonasal cancer: improved outcome compared to conventional radiotherapy. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys* 2010;78:998–1004
20. Shakhanova Sh. Sh., Rakhimov N. M., & Murodov Sh. T.. (2024). Aspects of sarcopenia syndrome in oncological practice: diagnosis and treatment. *The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research*, 6(02), 16–25.
21. Bristol IJ, Ahamad A, Garden AS, Morrison WH, Hanna EY, Papadimitrakopoulou VA et al. Postoperative radiotherapy for maxillary sinus cancer: long term outcomes and toxicities of treatment. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys* 2007;68:719–30
22. Brasnu D, Laccourreye O, Bassot V, Laccourreye L, Naudo P, Roux FX. Cisplatin-based neoadjuvant chemotherapy and combined resection for ethmoid sinus adenocarcinoma reaching and/or invading the skull base. *Arch Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg* 1996;122:765–68
23. Dulguerov P, Allal AS. Nasal and paranasal sinus carcinoma: how can we continue to make progress? *Curr Opin Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg* 2006;14:67–72